

WAYS TO IMPROVE THE EFFICIENCY OF SERVICES BY ASSESSING RISKS IN THE BANKING SECTOR IN THE PROCESS OF ECONOMIC TRANSFORMATION

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ПУТИ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ УСЛУГ ПУТЕМ ОЦЕНКИ РИСКОВ В БАНКОВСКОМ СЕКТОРЕ В ПРОЦЕССЕ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ

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Abstract

This research work explores ways to improve the efficiency of services in the banking sector by assessing risks in the process of economic transformation. The banking sector is a key element of the economy and its efficiency plays an important role in ensuring the stability and growth of the economic system. However, in the context of economic transformation associated with changes in the political, social and economic environment, banks face new risks that can significantly affect their effectiveness. The results of the work may be useful for banking institutions, regulators and other stakeholders who seek to improve the efficiency of services in the banking sector in the context of economic transformation.

Аннотация

Данная работа исследует пути повышения эффективности услуг в банковском секторе путем оценки рисков в процессе экономической трансформации. Банковский сектор является ключевым элементом экономики, и его эффективность играет важную роль в обеспечении стабильности и роста экономической системы. Однако в условиях экономической трансформации, связанной с изменениями в политической, социальной и экономической среде, банки сталкиваются с новыми рисками, которые могут существенно влиять на их эффективность. Результаты работы могут быть полезны для банковских учреждений, регуляторных органов и других заинтересованных сторон, которые стремятся повысить эффективность услуг в банковском секторе в условиях экономической трансформации.

Keywords: transformation, risk assessment, service efficiency, bank, efficiency.

Ключевые слова: трансформация, оценка рисков, эффективность услуг, банк, эффективность.

Introduction.

Uzbekistan has begun implementing much-needed reforms in the banking sector. In order to prevent financial problems, financial liberalization should be carried out along with the strengthening of institutions, and for

this purpose, the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan is improving the system of regulation and control of banking activities.

Ways to improve the efficiency of services through risk assessment in the banking sector in the process of economic transformation are as follows:

Figure 1. Ways to improve the efficiency of services through risk assessment in the banking sector in the process of economic transformation¹

Based on international experience, along with the reforms implemented by the government in the banking sector, it is important to consistently reform state enterprises and the business environment, and to strengthen competition. These ways help banks to improve their effectiveness in explaining, assessing and managing risks. Their implementation allows to improve the used

methods of risk detection, assessment and management of banks.

At the same time, without destabilizing credit booms, the most urgent reforms that will help ensure the banking system with the credit necessary for a successful transition to a market economy include the following key areas (table#1).

¹ Prepared by the author.

Key directions of banks for a successful transition to a market economy²

State bank management and lending based on state policy.	State-owned banks (at least those at the top of the privatization list) should be freed from political interference in their lending, preferably by presidential decree. All other official and "hidden" directed lending must be correctly recorded in the "directed loan portfolio" and reflected in the financial statements of the State Bank of Russia, so that the supervisory body (Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan), the owner (Ministry of Finance), investors and the public can monitor the dynamics of its volume and quality. It is necessary for the Ministry of Finance to clearly define the objectives of the development of state-owned banks, to provide "state services" to state banks and to establish mechanisms to ensure transparency and accountability of fiscal expenditures related to them.
Credit risk reporting, management and control.	The Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan should improve control over credit quality by conducting thematic analyzes related to credit quality (for example, how banks assess the solvency of borrowers). Over time, the CBR should strengthen its ability to conduct targeted horizontal credit quality checks and a broader review of banks' asset quality. This initial review and gradual capacity building is necessary to better understand the size and dynamics of NPLs and their impact on bank capital buffers. It is necessary for the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan to improve the methodology for classifying problem loans (or more broadly, assets), including the predictive approach and ensuring its application by banks. Also, the registry should strengthen control over the quality of credit reporting and the exchange of credit information. The Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan should put pressure on all banks to improve the corporate governance system, internal control, risk management, and standards for assessing borrowers' solvency. The banking market should further strengthen the system of monitoring, control, exit and crisis preparedness.
Mobilization of deposits.	Banks of Uzbekistan have not succeeded in attracting deposits due to the historical distrust of the population in their services. At the same time, the banking system has access to state credit lines (especially the State Bank) and has recently managed to attract external debt funds in national currency. It follows that the incentive to attract internal contributions is weak. In the medium and long term, Uzbekistan will have to rely more on additional funds from foreign funds for its development. However, attracting domestic deposits can contribute to the stability of banks' funding structure and help households and businesses build financial wealth and hedge risk. In turn, more resilient households and businesses reduce credit risk for banks.
Product development.	There are a number of products that the market could develop in the short term with government support to help strengthen the sustainability of credit intermediation. For example, in order to reduce the risks of credit concentration and help the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan to introduce stricter standards, it is possible to improve the credit syndication system, including with the participation of foreign banks. Despite the fact that banks have recently been able to attract foreign financing in soums, financing in foreign currency will continue. The development of the hedging market (over the counter or through the stock exchange) helps to reduce the currency risk of banks and borrowers. In addition, agriculture is an integral part of the economy of Uzbekistan, which can be competitive in the long term. To remain competitive, agricultural finance products supported by government policies, such as seasonally adjusted finance and disaster insurance, are required to address climate risk and reduce credit risk in agricultural finance, where the market can develop. The banking system should continue to promote rapid digital payment systems and solutions to facilitate e-business as well as broader digitization and market integration.

Banks may face a multifaceted challenge thanks to six key trends: to be more effective in identifying and mitigating risks, to be more efficient and faster in supporting business and meeting customer needs, and to support decision-making across the organization - better adaptation and better preparation for support. to meet regulatory requirements.

We believe our recommended vision for the risk function in 2025 will address these issues, but this fu-

ture risk function will be significantly different from today's in many areas. In 2025, risk functions in banks have the potential to be the primary architects of seamless, unbiased risk decisions and monitoring across the organization. They can deliver superior value by reducing risk and operational costs, contributing to a more intuitive customer experience, and helping the bank manage compliance. This view includes a risk function that controls the following actions:

² Prepared by the author during the course of research.

Model, simplify, standardize, and automate regulatory processes to minimize manual intervention, deliver superior customer experiences, take advantage of big data, and reverse decisions. This is expected to significantly reduce non-financial risk and reduce operational costs of the risk function.

Closer collaboration with the business – for example, reimagined customer journeys or joint operational risk reduction – and with other functions, for example with strategic planners on balance sheet optimization. It helps the bank to respond to new regulations, develop an attractive customer experience, make bad decisions, solve emerging types of risks and reduce costs.

To be a strong advocate of corporate values and principles through a stronger risk culture that is defined, communicated and reinforced across the Bank. On-site risk identification, assessment and mitigation is part of the daily work of all employees throughout the organization. Various initiatives help establish the mindsets and behaviors that make up this risk culture.

Build and manage new models and datasets, develop and hire people with diverse skills who can collaborate with business and other functions.

The risk function is likely to be stronger in all areas of the organization. To make these changes, it will need to transform its operating model, processes, IT/data infrastructure and talent pool.

Operational model

The operating model is expected to change significantly as analytical services and advisory and consulting relationships become important parts of risk management. For example, the risk function should be able to work with strategy to proactively manage all regulatory constraints. It must also build analytical capabilities to handle all current and new models and analytical approaches, such as machine learning.

During this transition, some areas stay the same size but change focus. For example, the risk management function will likely benefit from a shared model, engaging more with the business and other functions to improve customer journeys and product offerings, reducing non-financial risks at their source and helping the bank's overall strategy.

The risk function is also expected to take on new responsibilities for stakeholder management, de-biasing, regulatory governance and emerging risks. His personal and industrial activities are probably fueled by his focus on managing internal and external stakeholders, and he sets up a de-biasing department to help train relevant employees in unsavory ways. In addition, the risk-process task force can instill the concept of continuous improvement and zero-based process redesign in the risk organization. New teams can focus on the types of risks that banks are expected to face (eg model, contagion and cyber-attacks). As a result, some parts of the risk function will probably need more resources than they do today, such as those covering new types of risk.

Procedures

Some areas, including manual processes and risk reporting, may require fewer resources through simplification, standardization and automation. While risk decision-making is expected to be firmly embedded in end-to-end customer journeys, key processes are more

likely to be paperless, automated, and handled in real-time. The division of tasks between machines and humans will be much different than it is today. People review only selected cases that do not conform to bank policy, approve decision proposals, and review highly complex cases. This is expected to apply to retail and small and medium businesses as well. Automation also offers great opportunities for wholesale banking services when extending credit or making credit decisions for trade finance or receivables finance products for existing customers.

Non-financial risks provide another great opportunity to bring management directly into core processes. In operational risk, we expect human activities to focus on eliminating risk at source, designing key risk indicators (KRIs), implementing control points, and establishing incident management procedures. Many other activities, including monitoring, are expected to be automated over time. As a result, the number of compliance officers will likely be reduced; for example, financial crime detection relies on models such as machine learning.

IT/data infrastructure

The supporting IT infrastructure and data can take many forms, although recent trends rely on "dual-speed architectures" and data lakes. A two-tier architecture divides a bank's IT architecture into a slower, reliable backend (eg, the bank's core IT systems, often older systems) and a flexible, agile customer-oriented frontend. A data lake collects and stores all types of data, structured and unstructured, internal and external. It is not necessary to follow strict rules when entering data into the bank (as is required to enter data into the enterprise database). Instead, data users define the rules for retrieving data from the lake. Combining this flexibility with Google-like search technology, the data lake provides a step-change that helps banks leverage their data for multiple purposes, from marketing to risk to finance. The system's scale and flexibility help banks use big data tools to verify and analyze complex data.

Achieving the target state is expected to be costly, especially in terms of systems and infrastructure. While staying on top can make such investments vital, the cost pressures described here probably make this a trivial task. Some banks may be left behind because they are unable or unwilling to make these investments.

Talent pool

Talent and resources in the risk function will need to move to analysis, collaboration and other new areas of responsibility in the function; however, much fewer people are expected to participate in manual risk decision-making. New hires will likely have advanced mathematical and statistical backgrounds, be experts in machine learning and other sophisticated data analysis techniques, and work well with other parts of the bank to transform data. can be business translators. concepts of business activities. As these risk managers become trusted advisors to businesses, they can be expected to provide a strong contrast to today's operators and professionals who focus more on case review.

As banks search for the best candidates for these positions, they can compete directly with technology

firms for the best candidates. Partnerships with universities and financial technology companies will help banks acquire this talent. To win these candidates, the risk function must reshape its employee value proposition and align it with these new hires. The function must also change its culture to one that promotes entrepreneurship and creativity. These new hires will likely need training and development to keep them abreast of emerging trends in a complex technology environment with advanced digital tools.

Conclusion:

As a result of the research, we came to the following conclusion:

1. Risk assessment is an integral part of the banking industry and plays an important role in improving the efficiency of services. It allows banks to identify, measure and manage risks associated with the provision of services, as well as to develop appropriate strategies and measures to minimize them.

2. The implementation of a risk assessment system in the banking sector helps to identify threats and opportunities that may be related to the provision of services. This allows banks to develop and implement effective strategies aimed at reducing risks and increasing the efficiency of their activities.

3. Risk assessment helps banks adapt to changing market conditions and economic environment. By identifying and managing the risks associated with financial operations and investments, the bank can optimize its business processes, improve the efficiency of its services and strengthen its competitiveness.

4. Risk assessment helps to improve the quality of services in the banking sector. By identifying and managing the risks associated with financial transactions, the bank can ensure the reliability, recklessness and integrity of its services, which contributes to customer satisfaction and trust.

5. Implementation of the risk assessment system requires appropriate expertise, methodological development and technological support. However, the results of the study show that these costs are justified by increasing the efficiency of services, reducing possible risks and improving the bank's financial performance.

Overall, evidence-based research confirms that risk assessment is an important tool for improving service performance in the banking industry. The implementation of the risk assessment system allows banks to make informed decisions, minimize risks, improve the quality of services and increase their competitiveness in the market.

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